

A STUDY IN THE COMPLEX FORMATION OF BERYLLIUM IONS WITH HYDROXY-CARBOXYLIC ACIDS

BY I. D. VARMA AND R. C. MEHROTRA

It has been shown by electrometric titrations that compared to aliphatic α -hydroxy-acids, salicylic acid is a better chelating agent for beryllium ions. The nature of complexes formed by beryllium with salicylate ions has been investigated in detail by electrometric and conductometric titrations, and a plausible mechanism has been suggested for the titration curves obtained. The correctness of the suggested mechanism has been demonstrated by quantitative analysis of the products of various reactions. Alternative and more convenient methods have been described for the preparation of the complex salts: $\text{Be}[\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_2[\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2] \cdot 11\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Although studies have recently been carried out on the complexes formed by beryllium ions in aqueous solutions (Takeshi and Furuhashi, *Bull. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res., Japan*, 1943, 22, 367; Purkayastha, *this Journal*, 1947, 24, 257; Meek and Banks, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4108), not much systematic physicochemical work, however, appears to have been carried out on the complexes formed by beryllium ions with salicylic acid and other aliphatic α -hydroxy-acids like glycollic acid and its substituted products, lactic and mandelic acids. A survey of the literature reveals that the preparations of some complex salts of the above acids with beryllium have already been described (Parson and Sargent, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 31, 1203; Rosenheim and Lehmann, *Annalen*, 1924, 440, 153; Jones *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 563; Asmussen and Madsen, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 212, 321).

The nature of complex species present, when beryllium ions are treated with salicylate ions in aqueous solution, has been investigated by the following electrometric and conductometric titrations:

- (i) Electrometric titration of beryllium sulphate (BeSO_4) and basic beryllium sulphate $\text{Be}(\text{OH})(\text{SO}_4)_{0.5}$ with salts of salicylic acid and other aliphatic α -hydroxy acids.
- (ii) Electrometric and conductometric titration of beryllium sulphate alone and in the presence of 1, 2 and 4 moles of potassium salicylate with alkali.

EXPERIMENTAL

Beryllium sulphate (B.D.H.-Analar) was crystallised three times from conductivity water and analysed. The analyses corresponded to $\text{BeSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Salicylic acid (B.D.H.-Analar) was also crystallised from hot conductivity water. The solution of potassium salicylate was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of salicylic acid in an equivalent quantity of KOH solution. Standard solutions of $\text{Be}(\text{OH})\text{Cl}$ and $\text{Be}(\text{OH})(\text{SO}_4)_{0.5}$ were obtained by adding one equivalent of the alkali to a standard solution of normal beryllium salts and making up to a known volume.

p_n measurements were carried out in a thermostatically controlled room (temp. $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$) with a Philips p_n -measuring apparatus, G.M. 4491/G.M. 4493. A glass electrode gave readings reproducible to $\pm 0.005 p_n$.

Conductometric measurements were carried out in a thermostat ($35^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$) with the help of a resistance measuring assembly, Philips G.M. 4429 and an Emerson cell, G.M. 4221.

Electrometric Titration.--Electrometric titrations were carried out by adding the reagent from a micropipette to 20 c.c. of the solution containing beryllium ions. The p_n was noted after stirring gently the solution for two minutes and waiting for another two minutes. Two such readings were obtained for every addition of the reagent, and these were found to be almost identical in every case. For sake of brevity the actual p_n observations and the plotted graph (Table I; curve 1, Fig. 1) are both recorded here for one system only and for the rest, only the graph has been given.

TABLE I
System: 20 c.c. of $M/40\text{-BeSO}_4$ + K-salicylate.

$M/2\text{-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{K}$ added.	p_n of the system.	$M/2\text{-C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{K}$ added.	p_n of the system.
0.0 c.c.	3.435	1.5 c.c.	3.015
0.1	3.125	1.6	3.030
0.2	3.015	1.7	3.045
0.3	2.975	1.8	3.060
0.4	2.955	1.9	3.075
0.5	2.945	2.0	3.090
0.6	2.945	2.2	3.125
0.7	2.945	2.4	3.160
0.8	2.950	2.6	3.190
0.9	2.955	2.8	3.220
1.0	2.965	3.0	3.255
1.1	2.975	3.2	3.295
1.2	2.985	3.4	3.325
1.3	2.995	3.6	3.355
1.4	3.005	3.8	3.385
		4.0	3.415

Conductometric Titrations.--The conductometric titrations were carried out by adding $M/2$ alkali from a micropipette to a solution of beryllium sulphate ($M/80$, 40 c. c.) in presence of the requisite quantity of potassium salicylate. The solution was stirred for fifteen minutes and left for another five minutes before noting the readings. Such an operation gave constant values for every reading as well as ensured that the solution attained the temperature of the bath fully. Here also, the actual readings (Table II; curve 2, Fig. 3) are given for one system only, and for the rest, only graphs are shown in Fig. 3.

TABLE II

System : 40 c.c. of $M/80\text{-BeSO}_4$ + 1 c.c. K. sal. + NH_4OH .

$M/2\text{-NH}_4\text{OH}$ added.	$1/R$ of the system $\times 10^{-3}$.	$M/2\text{-NH}_4\text{OH}$ added	$1/R$ of the system $\times 10^{-3}$.
0.0 c.c.	3.533	2.2 c.c.	5.813
0.2	3.636	2.4	5.813
0.4	3.676	2.6	5.813
0.6	3.802	2.8	5.813
0.8	3.845	3.0	5.813
1.0	4.000	3.2	5.813
1.2	4.347	3.4	5.813
1.4	4.739	3.6	5.813
1.6	4.926	3.8	5.813
1.8	5.236	4.0	5.813
2.0	5.586		

$\text{Be}[\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ or $\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.—To a solution of BeSO_4 (2.2141 g. in 500 c.c. H_2O) containing 25 c.c. of $M/2\text{-C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3\text{K}$ (molar ratio of $\text{BeSO}_4 : \text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3\text{K} = 1 : 1$) was added gradually 12.5 c.c. of $M\text{-KOH}$ solution (1 mole). The reaction mixture was concentrated to 50 c.c. From the concentrate, potassium sulphate was completely precipitated by addition of 100 c.c. of absolute alcohol. The filtrate was allowed to evaporate to dryness at 60° to a white shining crust. The crust was powdered and repeatedly crystallised from conductivity water to give crystals of $\text{Be}[\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2]$ or $\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2$, dried at $90\text{--}95^\circ$ and cooled in a desiccator. The compound is hygroscopic, sparingly soluble in water, alcohol, benzene and acetone. { Found : Be, 5.195. Calc. for $\text{Be}[\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{Be}, 4.98\%$ }. This confirms the fact that the reaction among BeSO_4 (1 mole), $\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3\text{K}$ (1 mole) and KOH (1 mole) may be represented as :

$\text{K}_2[\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2]$.—(a). To a solution of BeSO_4 (2.215 g. in 500 c.c.) containing 25 c.c. of $M/2\text{-C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3\text{K}$ (molar ratio of $\text{BeSO}_4 : \text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3\text{K} = 1 : 1$) was added gradually 25 c.c. of $M\text{-KOH}$ (2 moles). The solution was left for 2 hours after which the precipitated mass was filtered off, washed with cold water and ignited to BeO . The filtrate was concentrated to 50 c.c. On addition of 100 c.c. of absolute alcohol to the concentrate, potassium sulphate was completely precipitated. On evaporation of the alcoholic filtrate to dryness at 60° , a faintly pink crust was obtained. It was finally powdered and repeatedly crystallised from water and dried at 100° , and cooled in a desiccator. A white crystalline powder, soluble in water, dilute mineral acids, moderately soluble in alcohol and sparingly soluble in ammonia and alkalis, was obtained which was analysed. { Found : Be, 2.38 ; K, 20.81 ; $\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3$, 74.01. Calc. for $\text{K}_2[\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{Be}, 2.38 ; \text{K}, 20.71 ; \text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3, 72.12\%$ }.

Alkaline permanganate was used for determination of salicylate ions (Bottger and Oesper, "Newer Methods of Volumetric Chemical Analysis", pp. 55-65).

The reaction among BeSO_4 (1 mole), $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{K}$ (1 mole) and KOH (2 moles), represented by the following equation, was further confirmed by estimating the amount of precipitated beryllium hydroxide, the amounts of complex salt $\text{K}_2[\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2]$ and also of K_2SO_4 formed in the reaction.

(b). To a solution of BeSO_4 (2.217 g. in 500 c.c. H_2O) containing 50 c.c. of $M/2$ - $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{K}$ (molar ratio of $\text{BeSO}_4 : \text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{K} = 1 : 2$) was added gradually 25 c.c. of M - KOH (2 moles). The clear solution, thus obtained, was concentrated to 50 c.c. Potassium sulphate was completely precipitated by addition of absolute alcohol to the concentrate. The filtrate (free of K_2SO_4) was allowed to evaporate at 60° , yielding a white crust which was dried at 100° and cooled in a desiccator. The product was purified by crystallisation from water. The crystalline powder, which was similar to the complex salt described above, was obtained and analysed. { Found : Be, 2.38 ; K, 20.80 ; $\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3$, 74.0. Calc. for $\text{K}_2[\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$: Be, 2.38 ; K, 20.71 ; $\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3$, 72.12% }.

The fact that the following reaction among BeSO_4 (1 mole), $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{K}$ (2 moles) and KOH (2 moles) is quantitative, has been further shown by estimating the amount of K_2SO_4 and the complex salt formed by known amounts of the reactants :

DISCUSSION

The electrometric titration of beryllium sulphate with potassium salicylate (curve 1, Fig. 2) indicates a chelation of the type

This chelation by the donation of a lone pair of electrons from the hydroxyl oxygen atom makes the "hydrogen" atom more labile and acidic, and thus, the extent of lowering in the p_H of the system (curve 1, Fig. 1) is a direct measure of the above type of chelation. As shown in a recent study with zirconium mandelate (Kapoor and Mehrotra, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, **10B**, 304), also the extent of chelation increases with the rise of p_H of the solution (curves 2 and K_1 , Fig. 1). A comparison of curves K_1 , K_2 , K_3 and K_4 and also of 1, 2, 3 and 4 (Fig. 1) indicate that chelation of the above type is much less in the case of aliphatic hydroxy-acids (glycollic, lactic and mandelic acids) compared to salicylic acid.

FIG. 1

Curves 1, 2, 3 and 4: 20 c.c. $M/40\text{-BeSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ soln. titrated with $M/2\text{-K}$ salts of salicylic, mandelic, glycollic and lactic acids, respectively.

Curves K_1 , K_2 , K_3 and K_4 : 20 c.c. $M/40\text{-Be(OH)(SO}_4)_0.5$ soln. titrated with $M/2\text{-K}$ salts of the respective acids as above.

Curve K_1 : 20 c.c. $M/40\text{-Be(OH)Cl}$ titrated with $M/2\text{-K-Sal.}$ soln.

FIG. 2

Curves 1-4: Titration of 20 c.c. $M/40\text{-BeSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ soln. containing 0, 1, 2 and 4 moles of $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{K}$ respectively with $M/2\text{-KOH}$ soln.

In view of the strong chelation shown by salicylate ions, it was considered of interest to investigate the system more fully. The results obtained can be explained as noted below.

The electrometric titration (curve K_1 , Fig. 1) of $\text{Be}(\text{OH})(\text{SO}_4)_2$ with potassium salicylate ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{K}$) indicates a small fall in p_{H} for the first mole of salicylate and a comparatively large fall in p_{H} for the second mole of salicylate.

The fall in p_{H} in the above titration, however, continues even after the second mole of salicylate has been added. This might indicate further chelation of another mole of salicylate, but this is very improbable due to the maximum covalency of beryllium being four. The above therefore indicates that further amount of salicylate shifts the equilibrium (iii) to the right, and thus slightly lowers the p_{H} of the medium. This conclusion is supported by the results of the titrations also. That the anion of the beryllium salts does not take part in the above complex formation is shown by the similar nature of the curve K'_1 (Fig. 1) in which case $\text{Be}(\text{OH})\text{Cl}$ has been titrated with $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{K}$.

The electrometric titration (curve 2, Fig. 2) of $[\text{BeSO}_4 + \text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{K}]$ with KOH indicates a slow rise in p_{H} of the solution initially due to the following neutralisation:

The above mechanism is supported by the isolation of beryllium salicylate ($\text{BeC}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$) by the treatment of one mole of BeSO_4 with a mole each of $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{K}$ and KOH . The p_{H} (3.4) at half neutralisation indicates the dissociation constant of the order of $10^{-3.4}$ (3.5×10^{-4}) for the corresponding acid:

The neutral beryllium monosalicylate may be assigned the alternative structure $\text{Be}[\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2]$ (Jones *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). This easily explains the titration curve 2 (Fig. 2). After the addition of the first mole of alkali, the titration curve is quite similar to the titration curve of beryllium sulphate itself with alkali (curve 1, Fig. 2), and it may therefore be explained by the following simple reaction :

The above conclusions have been further supported by the isolation of $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{K}_2[\text{Be}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2]$ almost in equimolecular quantities when BeSO_4 is treated with two moles of KOH in presence of 1 mole of $\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3\text{K}$.

The titration (curve 3, Fig. 2) of BeSO_4 with alkali in presence of 2 moles of $\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3\text{K}$ can be explained simply as :

The stability of (I) is indicated by the non-precipitation of $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$, even after the p_n of the medium exceeds 11 in the presence of higher hydroxyl-ion concentration. The titration (curve 4, Fig. 2) in the presence of 4 moles of salicylate ions confirms the above conclusion. The earlier portion of the curve 4 is higher than curve 3 due to the presence of basic salicylate ions, but in the range of 1-2 moles, this effect is counterbalanced and even surpassed due to the shift of equilibrium (v) to the right.

The conductometric titrations on similar systems were first carried out with potassium hydroxide, but these did not provide sharp inflection points (curves K_1 , K_2 and K_3 , Fig. 3). When potassium hydroxide was replaced by the weak base, ammonium hydroxide, the above titration yielded very sharp inflection points. As the excess of ammonium hydroxide increases the conductivity of the medium only very negligibly, the end-point is indicated very sharply.

The titration (curve A_1 , Fig. 3) of BeSO_4 with NH_4OH in presence of 1 mole of $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{K}$ can be explained on the following lines :

showing a small rise in conductivity due to replacement of complex beryllium ion by smaller NH_4^+ . The neutral beryllium monosalicylate has a very small conductivity

as shown by Jones *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). With a further mole of NH_4OH the following reaction may be assumed to be occurring :

FIG. 3

Curves K_1 , K_2 and K_3 : Titration of 40 c.c. of $M/80\text{-BeSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ soln. containing 1, 2 and 4 moles respectively of $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{K}$ with $M/2\text{-KOH}$ soln.

Curves A_1 , A_2 and A_3 : Titration of 40 c.c. of $M/80\text{-BeSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ soln. containing 1, 2 and 4 moles respectively of $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{K}$ with $M/2\text{-NH}_4\text{OH}$.

The titration (curve A_2 , Fig. 3) in the presence of 2 moles of $\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_3\text{K}$ is similar to A_1 although showing a less sharp inflection at 1 mole, indicating that beryllium salicylate anion begins to get formed at an earlier stage. This inflection point disappears in curve

A, in the presence of excess of salicylate ions, indicating the formation of disalicylate ion from almost the beginning. The titration curve is almost horizontal after the addition of 2 moles of NH_4OH in every case, indicating that no higher complexes are formed in the system. The above conclusions from conductometric work therefore are in full accord with the conclusions from electrometric and preparative experiments.

The authors are grateful to Prof. Dr. A. C. Chatterji for making available necessary laboratory facilities for this work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW

Received November 15, 1957.